

System-Level Modeling of Acoustic and Environmental Sensors for AUV Simulation

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Abstract—System-level simulation is a key enabler for the design and evaluation of Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs), particularly in maritime and security-relevant scenarios. While existing simulation frameworks support communication, coordination, and energy modeling, sensor behavior is often represented in a simplified manner. This paper presents a modular abstraction for modeling acoustic and environmental sensors in discrete-event AUV simulations. The approach focuses on sampling behavior, uncertainty, detection characteristics, and energy consumption. A temperature sensor and a forward-looking sonar are implemented in an OMNeT++-based simulation environment and evaluated with respect to system-level performance.

Index Terms—Autonomous Underwater Vehicles, Sensor Modeling, OMNeT++, Maritime Simulation

I. INTRODUCTION

Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs) have become an essential component in a wide range of maritime applications, including environmental monitoring, offshore infrastructure inspection, and surveillance of critical underwater assets. In contrast to terrestrial or aerial systems, underwater operation is characterized by the absence of global navigation satellite systems and severely limited communication capabilities. As a consequence, AUVs must rely heavily on onboard sensing to perceive their environment, estimate their state, and support navigation and decision-making as discussed in [1] and [2].

The design and validation of AUV systems are inherently challenging due to the high cost, limited repeatability, and operational risks of real-world experiments. Simulation has therefore become an indispensable tool for the development and evaluation of AUV technologies. In particular, system-level simulation frameworks enable the investigation of communication behavior, coordination strategies, and energy consumption under controlled and reproducible conditions [3]. Recent work has emphasized modular and extensible simulation architectures for AUVs. Physics-based simulators such as Gazebo-based UUV frameworks focus on hydrodynamics and geometric realism, whereas discrete-event approaches such as OMNeT++ emphasize modularity, timing behavior, communication, and system-level interactions as apparent from [4] and [5]. In OMNeT++, system behavior is represented through interacting modules and scheduled events, making it suitable for modeling periodic sensing processes. This makes OMNeT++ particularly suitable for studying sensing behavior together with energy consumption and event-driven subsystem interactions.

Despite these advances, sensor modeling in system-level simulations remains comparatively underrepresented. In many existing approaches, sensors are treated as idealized data

sources that provide perfect and instantaneous measurements. Such simplifications neglect key aspects of real-world sensing, including temporal sampling behavior, measurement uncertainty, and probabilistic detection characteristics. This abstraction gap becomes particularly critical in maritime scenarios, where perception performance directly affects navigation safety, obstacle avoidance, and mission success.

From a system perspective, sensors constitute the primary interface between the AUV and its environment, as all higher-level functions ultimately depend on sensor data. Errors and uncertainties introduced at the sensing level propagate through estimation and control algorithms and can significantly influence overall system behavior. Consequently, a realistic yet computationally efficient representation of sensor behavior is essential for meaningful system-level studies.

This paper addresses this gap by introducing a structured abstraction for modeling acoustic and environmental sensors in discrete-event AUV simulations. The proposed approach focuses on system-relevant characteristics, including sampling behavior, uncertainty, detection properties, and energy consumption, while avoiding computationally expensive physical modeling. The abstraction is designed to integrate seamlessly into modular OMNeT++-based simulation architectures and to support comparative studies of different sensing strategies.

To demonstrate the applicability of the approach, the proposed models are implemented within an OMNeT++-based AUV simulation framework and evaluated in representative scenarios. The evaluation focuses on the influence of sensor parameters on system-level behavior, including perception performance and resource usage.

II. BACKGROUND AND SENSOR CHARACTERISTICS

Sensors constitute the primary interface between an AUV and its environment, as all perception, navigation, and environmental understanding rely on sensor measurements. Accordingly, sensor selection and integration are central to AUV system design. In practice, measurements from multiple sensors are combined to obtain robust estimates of the vehicle state and its surroundings, motivating a structured representation of sensor characteristics in simulation environments.

A common classification distinguishes between proprioceptive and exteroceptive sensors. Proprioceptive sensors provide information about the internal state of the vehicle, including motion, orientation, and depth, and form the basis for navigation in GPS-denied environments [1], [2]. Exteroceptive sensors capture information about the external environment,

TABLE I
CLASSIFICATION OF AUV SENSORS ACCORDING TO THEIR FUNCTIONAL
ROLE AND SENSING PRINCIPLE.

Functional class	Operation principle	Typical Examples	Role in Simulation
Proprioceptive	Mostly passive	IMU (Accelerometer/Gyro), pressure sensor, DVL (velocity), encoders.	Baseline state estimation.
Exteroceptive	Active	Sonar (FLS, Side-scan), cameras, magnetometers, USB/LBL.	Supports obstacle sensing and environment interaction through emitted signals.
Exteroceptive	Passive	Temperature sensor, magnetometer, camera	Samples environmental properties without emitting a probing signal

such as obstacles or environmental properties, and are therefore essential for situational awareness and mission execution.

Sensors can further be categorized according to their sensing principle. Passive sensors observe naturally available physical quantities, whereas active sensors emit a probing signal and analyze the response. This distinction is particularly relevant in underwater environments, where acoustic sensing dominates. Table I summarizes the functional and operational classification of AUV sensors and their roles in system-level simulation.

Acoustic sensors play a central role in underwater systems due to the favorable propagation characteristics of sound. Forward-looking sonar (FLS) is particularly relevant for obstacle detection and situational awareness, as it provides real-time information about the environment in front of the vehicle. However, it does not directly provide absolute position information and is therefore typically combined with additional sensors and estimation methods.

Environmental sensors complement acoustic sensing by providing information about physical properties of the water. Temperature sensors are widely used due to their robustness and low energy consumption. In addition, temperature variations influence the speed of sound in water and thereby affect acoustic propagation, impacting both sonar-based sensing and underwater communication [3].

For system-level simulation, the focus lies on abstract sensor properties rather than detailed hardware characteristics. The most relevant properties are the sampling rate, measurement uncertainty, and energy consumption, as they directly affect temporal resolution, robustness, and resource usage. The sampling rate is typically modeled as a periodic event, while uncertainty is represented using stochastic models such as additive noise. Energy consumption is captured through abstract cost models reflecting sampling, processing, and communication.

These properties form the basis for the abstraction developed in this work and enable the analysis of trade-offs between perception quality, robustness, and resource usage.

III. SYSTEM-LEVEL SENSOR MODELING APPROACH

Sensor modeling in simulation ranges from detailed physics-based approaches to abstract representations. Physics-based models capture signal propagation, environmental interaction, and hardware characteristics, but are computationally expensive and often tightly coupled to specific frameworks.

System-level simulation instead focuses on the interaction between system components and their impact on overall behavior. Accordingly, the objective is not to reproduce exact physical processes, but to capture those characteristics that influence system-level performance. This perspective is particularly relevant for discrete-event frameworks such as OMNeT++, where system dynamics are event-driven.

The approach proposed in this work models sensors as discrete-time systems that periodically generate measurements. Each sensor is described by abstract parameters capturing sampling behavior, uncertainty, detection characteristics, and energy consumption. Such abstractions are common in system-level modeling of cyber-physical systems, where simplified models are used to evaluate design trade-offs [6].

A. Sensor as a Discrete-Time System

Each sensor is modeled as a discrete-time process producing measurements at a defined sampling interval, which determines temporal resolution and directly affects perception performance and resource usage.

Formally, the sensor is described by

$$y_k = h(x_k, E_k) + \eta_k, \quad (1)$$

where x_k denotes the vehicle state (e.g., position and orientation), E_k the relevant environmental state, $h(\cdot)$ the ideal sensor-specific measurement function, and η_k a stochastic noise term representing measurement uncertainty.

This formulation captures the dependency of sensor outputs on both system and environment and enables explicit modeling of uncertainty, which is essential for robustness analysis. The sensor abstraction thereby acts as an interface between the simulated environment and higher-level modules, generating event-based measurements.

B. Sensor Interface and Data Representation

Sensors are implemented using a unified interface that produces timestamped output messages containing measurements and associated metadata. The output structure depends on the sensor type, ranging from scalar values for environmental sensors to beam-wise detection lists containing obstacle distance and confidence information for acoustic sensors.

This abstraction enables integration into a common processing pipeline while preserving sensor-specific characteristics and supporting extensibility and comparability of different sensor configurations.

C. Uncertainty and Noise Modeling

Measurement uncertainty is modeled using simplified stochastic processes. For scalar environmental sensors such as the temperature sensor, additive Gaussian noise is applied to the sampled value, whereas the forward-looking sonar combines probabilistic detection with additional Gaussian range noise. While this abstraction does not capture all physical

effects, it provides sufficient realism for analyzing the impact of uncertainty on navigation, detection, and decision-making.

In particular, it enables the study of how sensor noise propagates through estimation algorithms and influences system-level performance.

D. Energy Consumption Modeling

Energy consumption is a key constraint in AUV operation. In the proposed abstraction, passive sensors such as the temperature sensor are modeled using continuous power consumption over time, whereas active sensors such as the forward-looking sonar consume energy per emitted ping event. This distinction reflects the different operational behavior of passive and active sensing modalities while remaining lightweight enough for system-level simulation. This captures the energy required for sensing, processing, and communication, enabling the evaluation of sensing strategies with respect to the overall energy budget. This approach is consistent with energy modeling in communication and mobility studies [3].

E. Integration into OMNeT++

The proposed abstraction integrates into an OMNeT++-based AUV simulation framework by modeling sensors as independent modules generating measurement events. These events are processed by other components, such as navigation and control modules, enabling closed-loop system simulation.

The design aligns with the architecture proposed in [4] and supports the integration of heterogeneous components within a unified framework. This enables comprehensive system-level studies combining sensing, communication, and coordination.

IV. SENSOR MODELS

To demonstrate the applicability of the proposed abstraction, two representative sensor types are modeled: a temperature sensor as an environmental sensor and a forward-looking sonar as an acoustic perception sensor. These sensors represent sensing paradigms commonly used in maritime applications.

A. Temperature Sensor Model

The temperature sensor is modeled as a passive environmental sensor providing scalar measurements of the surrounding water temperature. Instead of detailed oceanographic modeling, the temperature distribution is represented as a spatially discretized field that can be sampled at the AUV position, enabling efficient integration into discrete-event simulation. Fig. 1 illustrates the discretized temperature field, where each cell is associated with a temperature value. Sampling at the vehicle position enables the modeling of spatial gradients and localized variations. The measurement process follows the model introduced in Section III. At each sampling instant, the sensor retrieves the temperature value from the corresponding grid cell and applies stochastic noise, enabling the analysis of sampling and uncertainty effects. From a system-level perspective, the temperature sensor provides environmental information while also influencing acoustic propagation, as temperature variations affect the speed of sound in water. This impacts both sonar-based sensing and underwater communication [3]. The model allows the adjustment of sampling rate and noise characteristics, enabling the investigation of trade-offs between temporal resolution, measurement quality, and energy consumption.

Fig. 1. Spatially discretized temperature field used for environmental sensing.

Fig. 2. Geometric representation of the forward-looking sonar detection area.

B. Forward-Looking Sonar Model

The forward-looking sonar (FLS) is modeled as an active sensor detecting objects within a defined field of view. In contrast to environmental sensors, the sonar produces structured outputs representing detected objects. As shown in Fig. 2, the sonar is represented by a detection cone defined by a maximum range and opening angle. Objects within this region may be detected depending on their distance and sensor parameters.

Detection is modeled probabilistically using a distance-dependent sigmoid function, where detection probability decreases with increasing obstacle distance. For each beam, the resulting probability is evaluated through a Bernoulli trial to determine whether a detection occurs. This enables the representation of missed detections and false positives without requiring detailed acoustic modeling. The output is represented as a set of detections with associated attributes such as relative position or confidence, which can be processed by higher-level modules. Compared to physics-based approaches, the abstraction focuses on system-relevant characteristics, significantly reducing computational complexity while preserving the ability to evaluate detection performance [7]. From a system perspective, the sonar is critical for safe navigation, as it provides real-time obstacle information and directly affects collision avoidance and path planning.

V. EVALUATION

The proposed sensor abstraction is evaluated using representative simulation scenarios. The focus is on the influence of sensor parameters on system-level behavior rather than

Fig. 3. Influence of sampling rate on temperature estimation accuracy.

on physical accuracy. In particular, the impact of sampling rate, measurement uncertainty, and detection characteristics on perception performance and resource usage is analyzed.

A. Scenario Description

The evaluation is conducted within the OMNeT++-based AUV simulation framework described in previous sections. A single AUV operates in an environment with static obstacles and a spatially varying temperature field. The vehicle is equipped with the temperature sensor and forward-looking sonar introduced in Section IV. The temperature field is represented as a discretized grid, and obstacles are placed within the sonar’s operational area. Simulation parameters are varied systematically, including the sampling rate and noise level of the temperature sensor as well as the detection characteristics of the sonar.

B. Temperature Sensor Analysis

The temperature sensor is evaluated with respect to its ability to capture spatial variations. Different sampling rates are considered, ranging from low- to high-frequency measurements. Fig. 3 shows that low sampling rates fail to capture rapid spatial variations, resulting in higher estimation errors. Increasing the sampling rate improves accuracy but increases energy consumption. Measurement noise further reduces reliability, but its impact can be mitigated by higher sampling rates, highlighting a trade-off between measurement quality and resource usage.

C. Forward-Looking Sonar Analysis

The forward-looking sonar is evaluated in terms of detection performance as a function of distance and sensor configuration. As illustrated in Fig. 4, detection probability decreases with increasing distance. While obstacles are reliably detected at short ranges, detection becomes uncertain near the maximum range. The probabilistic model enables the analysis of missed detections and false positives. Missed detections may compromise safety, whereas false positives can lead to unnecessary avoidance maneuvers, emphasizing the importance of modeling detection uncertainty in system-level simulations.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a system-level abstraction for modeling acoustic and environmental sensors in AUV simulations.

Fig. 4. Detection probability of the forward-looking sonar as a function of distance.

Sensors are represented as discrete-time components characterized by sampling behavior, measurement uncertainty, detection properties, and energy consumption, enabling efficient integration into discrete-event frameworks such as OMNeT++.

The implementation of a temperature sensor and a forward-looking sonar demonstrates the applicability of the approach to both passive and active sensing. The evaluation shows that key system-level effects, including the impact of sampling rate, measurement uncertainty, and detection probability, can be captured with the proposed abstraction. In particular, the results highlight the trade-offs between perception quality and resource usage in energy-constrained AUV systems.

The approach bridges the gap between detailed physical models and simplified system-level representations, providing a practical basis for evaluating sensing strategies in maritime scenarios with manageable computational complexity.

Future work will extend the abstraction to additional sensor types and incorporate sensor fusion. Furthermore, cooperative multi-AUV scenarios and the interaction between sensing and communication will be investigated.

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